

Data Management Plan Information

Classes of errors in DOI names (Data Management Plan)

The data involved in this project are used to answer the following research questions: what are the classes of errors that characterize invalid DOIs? Which classes of errors can be addressed through automatic processes so as to get the correct DOIs? How many correct DOIs and, consequently, citations have been obtained by applying such automatic processing?

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Open Science Project 2020/2021

Organisations

Alma Mater Studiorum, Università di Bologna

Researchers

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Datasets

Title: Classes of errors in DOI names: code

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

Data Repositories

External Datasets

Registries

Services

This dataset contains the source code used to clean a CSV list of invalid DOI names and to output the correct ones, the classes of errors, and the ones that were not possible to fix automatically.

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

[To improve a product]

Comment: Correct errors in DOI names collected by COCI project from Crossref open citations.

1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

[Other]

Source code

1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

[Software - Java, C, Python]

Software written in python for cleaning CSV files containing invalid DOIs

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

[Primary data]

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

KB (kilobyte)

Comment: Usually Python scripts' sizes for solving this kind of tasks are measured in KB

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

[Researchers, Other]

Stakeholders in the Scholarly domain, involved in the collection and reuse of DOIs from secondary sources.

2 Reusable Data

2.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Yes

Peroni, S. (2021). Citations to invalid DOI-identified entities obtained from processing DOI-to-DOI citations to add in COCI (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4625300>

[To compare and combine with other data, To develop new products/ services]

2.2 Where do the data reside?

2.3 Which data will be re-used?

Citations to invalid DOI-identified entities obtained from processing DOI-to-DOI citations to add in COCI

3 FAIR Data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

No

3.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

3.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

3.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

No

3.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

No

3.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

Jupyter Python Notebook, Python Compiled File

3.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.21 Please describe if data require proprietary tools to access the data?

3.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.2 Making data openly accessible

3.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

all

3.2.4 How will the data be made available?

[Repository of Archive]

Zenodo, GitHub

3.2.6 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

3.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

3.2.10 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

never

3.3 Making data interoperable

3.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

No

3.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4 Increase data reuse

3.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?
immediately

3.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your
data?

Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and Licence 1.0

3.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of
your data?

No

3.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible,
interoperable and reusable be covered?

[Other]

4.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who
will be responsible for the management of your data?

No

Comment: The whole research team is responsible of the data management.

4.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the
management of the project data

4.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

[Other]

5 Data Security

5.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6 Ethical aspects

6.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on
data sharing?

No

6.2 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

[Not available]

7 Other

7.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Classes of errors in DOI names: output dataset

Template: Horizon 2020

External References

Data Repositories

External Datasets

Registries

Services

The output dataset consists of a CSV file reporting the classes of errors associated with various DOI names, the correct ones, and the ones that were not possible to fix automatically.

Dataset Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

[To obtain information, To improve a product, To combine with other data]

Comment: The data collected is intended to obtain which DOI names extracted from Crossref are found to be invalid, in order to produce a new dataset that contains the correct data. To do so, it is necessary to combine existing data with other data obtained through the DOI and Crossref APIs.

1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

[sample or specimen data]

The processed data is a sample of DOI names present in Crossref that were found to be invalid.

1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

[Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language), Other]

CSV format file.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

[Secondary data]

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

MB (megabyte)

Comment: An output of about 70 MB is expected, since the input weighs 60 MB, to which additional data that will be the result of the processing will be added.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

[Researchers, Research communities, Education, Industry]

This work is especially useful in the area of Scientometrics. Therefore, it is especially aimed at the world of research and the scientific community, as well as the related publishing industry.

2 Reusable Data

2.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Yes

Peroni, S. (2021). Citations to invalid DOI-identified entities obtained from processing DOI-to-DOI citations to add in COCI (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4625300>

[To compare and combine with other data, To develop new products/ services]

2.2 Where do the data reside?

2.3 Which data will be re-used?

3 FAIR Data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

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No

3.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

3.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

3.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

No

3.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

No

3.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

Python Compiled File, CSV Schema

3.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.21 Please describe if data require proprietary tools to access the data?

3.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.2 Making data openly accessible

3.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.2.2 Will your data be openly accessible?

all

3.2.4 How will the data be made available?

[Repository of Archive]

GitHub, Zenodo

3.2.6 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

3.2.7 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?

No

3.2.10 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

never

3.3 Making data interoperable

3.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?

No

3.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4 Increase data reuse

3.4.1 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?
immediately

3.4.4 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?

Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and Licence 1.0, Creative Commons Non-Commercial (Any)

3.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?

No

3.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

No

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

[Other]

Comment: The entire workflow will involve the use of open source and free infrastructures, such as GitHub and Zenodo. S.

4.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?

No

Comment: The whole research team is responsible of the data management.

4.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Comment: The output data will be shared on GitHub and Zenodo.

4.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?
[Other]

5 Data Security

5.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?
Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6 Ethical aspects

6.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.2 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?
[Not available]

7 Other

7.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?
No